

Securitization Dynamics in U.S. Banks: Impacts on Credit Supply, Capital Requirements, and Profitability

Author Name: Alsharif Alshater Bossely (ORCID: 0009-0004-2348-5749)

Affiliation (ITFC)

Email: abossely@itfc-idb.org

Abstract

This research explores the securitization activity in US banks between the year 2000 and year 2017. Our aim was to examine how the securitization in banks affected three aspects: the credit supply, capital requirements, and the profitability in US banks. Our research was based on data collected from thirty-three banks over an eighteen-year period. Our methodology was based on a panel linear regression analysis that adopts the approach of investigation of securitization trends and predictive interactions among those three financial variables. Our findings demonstrate a positive correlation between bank securitization activities and regulatory capital requirements. We also found a direct link between securitization and bank profitability. However, we couldn't confirm a connection between securitization and credit supply, despite suggestions in some prior literature.

Table of Contents

Contents

Abstract	2
Table of Contents.....	3
Abbreviations	4
1. Introduction.....	4
1.1 Background Info	4
1.2 Problem Statement.....	5
1.3 Research Hypothesis.....	6
1.4 Research Objectives	6
1.5 Research Methodology.....	6
1.6 Research Scope	6
1.7 Significance of the Study.....	7
1.8 Structure of the study	7
2. Theoretical Framework Literature Review	7
2.1 Theoretical Framework	7
2.2 Literature Review	7
2.2.1 Securitization and credit supply.....	8
2.2.2 Securitization and bank capital constraints	8
2.2.3 Securitization and profits	8
3. Methodology	9
3.1 Securitization and credit supply	11
3.2 Securitization and capital constraints	13
3.3 Securitization and profits.....	15
4. Empirical Results.....	17
4.1 Securitization and bank lending	17
4.2 Securitization and capital constraints	18
4.3 Securitization and bank profits	19
5. Conclusion	20
5.1 Summary of findings	20
5.2 Limitation of the Study.....	20
5.3 Suggestion for future research	20
Reference list.....	21

Abbreviations

CLO	<i>Collateralized loan obligation</i>
CDO	<i>Collateralized debt obligation</i>
EPS	<i>Earnings per share</i>
FE	<i>Fixed effects</i>
ROE	<i>Return on equity</i>

1. Introduction

Securitization and screening/risk-taking

1.1 Background Info

Asset securitization is essentially a process where illiquid loans and similar financial assets are bundled and sold to special purpose vehicles (SPVs). These SPVs then repackage the assets often through a process called tranching into securities that generate relatively predictable cash flows over time. Before they're brought to market, these instruments typically undergo credit enhancement to improve their ratings or perceived creditworthiness.

This method marked a shift from the traditional "originate-to-hold" approach (where banks kept loans on their books) to an "originate-to-distribute" model, which began gaining traction in the U.S. during the 1970s. Over the last forty-plus years, securitization has grown into one of the most significant financial innovations globally.

Before the 2007 financial crisis, securitization was widely embraced across the financial sector. But the events of 2007–2008 severely damaged its reputation, casting a long shadow over the practice. Today, securitization remains one of the most polarizing asset classes some see it as a clever and efficient banking tool, while others remain deeply skeptical.

Supporters argue that by transforming illiquid loans into marketable securities often structured in multiple tranches securitization can distribute risk more effectively across the market. It also opens up new channels of credit, creates relatively safe assets, and can reduce problems like adverse selection.

While these benefits aimed to enhance the overall financial industry's performance, it fell short of reassuring many of the investors. The Financial Times article titled "The missing piece of the securitization jigsaw" referred to a recent report authored by Janus Henderson's head of US securitized products (Kerschner, 2024)⁽¹⁾, who highlighted that some investors still have a bias against securitization. Several misconceptions persist regarding securitization, critics often incorrectly argue that securitized bonds inherently carry higher risk than corporate debt or that their credit ratings are fundamentally unreliable, credit ratings aren't trustworthy, securitization is a small asset class that can be ignored, and securitization is too hard to understand.

While on the one hand, this product is seen to have triggered one of the largest financial crises in history, it also is seen as a solution that brings social benefits of additional financing and risk-sharing, making it such a controversial product that divides opinions in the financial industry. Regulators, intermediaries, and investors should be aligned to reap the benefits of securitization and minimize this controversy. A Securitization Trilemma in Figure 1.1 refers to a divergence of the objectives of the three main stakeholders of the financial system. Without the right balance, investors may end up skeptical about securitization, regulators may end up facing challenges to keep an eye on securitization, and intermediaries may end up overloaded with tough regulations and skeptical investors.

Figure 1.1

Source: Author's own diagram

The study "Financial Intermediaries and Liquidity Creation" by Gary Gorton and George Pennacchi (1990) ⁽²⁾ mainly focused only on investors' appetite for intermediaries' liabilities, yet it did not cover the asset side of investing the proceeds from securitization and how would it affect the financials of the intermediaries. However, it provided good insight into the relationship between the three players (regulators, intermediaries, investors) through screening and risk sharing. The paper examined the role of financial intermediaries in mitigating trading losses due to information asymmetries.

To address the concerns about the risks associated with securitization and to make it more controlled after the financial crisis, regulators worked on reforming the securitization market. The reform included adding a retention requirement percentage for sponsors, enhancing transparency in the industry, and the ring-fencing of the core banking activities.

1.2 Problem Statement

The exponential expansion of asset-backed securities leading up to the 2007-08 global financial crisis was ultimately derailed by systemic failures within the subprime mortgage sector with the rising default in the subprime mortgage sector. The damage was spread across different markets and eventually resulted in a fully-fledged financial crisis that had a spillover effect on the rest of the world. Figure 1.2 shows a significant drop in asset backed securities volume from a peak of \$1.2 trillion in 2007 to a staggering \$250 billion in 2020.

Figure 1.2: The decline of the securitization market in the US

Source: Federal Reserve Bank St. Louis, "Asset-backed Commercial Paper Outstanding (ABCOMP)

The rapid growth of the U.S. shadow banking sector exposed a range of hidden vulnerabilities among them, distorted data, flawed risk models, and the consequences of regulatory arbitrage. While interest in securitization surged during and immediately after the financial crisis, both the volume of securitized products and related academic research have since lost momentum.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

This research examines three key hypotheses: first, whether securitization has contributed to an expansion in credit supply, second, its role in easing capital constraints for banking institutions, and third, whether securitization has positively influenced banks' net income. Together, these inquiries offer a comprehensive perspective on the broader implications of this complex financial interrelationship.

1.4 Research Objectives

Our objectives are:

- i) Analyze the Effect of Securitization on Credit Supply in US Banks and investigate the relationship between banks' securitization practices and their lending volumes.
- ii) To Assess the Impact of Securitization on the Capital Adequacy of US Banks and evaluate how securitization activities influence the capital buffers and regulatory capital requirements.
- iii) To Determine the Influence of Securitization on the Profitability of US Banks and examine whether securitization contributes positively or negatively to banks' bottom lines.

1.5 Research Methodology

In this research, we have applied a research technique aimed at identifying the securitization and the variables common trends in terms of interaction and predictive power of the variables. The initial phase of the analysis focused on exploring the co-movement and interactions between the volumes of securitization and three key variables. Specifically, we examined the loans-to-assets ratio as an indicator of credit supply. Subsequently, the relationship between the volumes of securitization and the equity-to-assets ratio was scrutinized as a measure of capital constraints. Finally, we assessed the connection between securitization volumes and net income, serving as an index for profitability. To examine the interdependencies among these variables, we conducted three separate regression analyses, treating each variable in turn as both independent and dependent, thus presenting and explaining the interrelationships between these variables.

1.6 Research Scope

- **Time-based Coverage:** The study will cover a period from 2000 to 2017, capturing various economic cycles to better understand the time-based dynamics of securitization.
- **Geographical Limitation:** The research will be limited to the United States banking sector.
- **Data Variables:** Data includes banks' balance sheet information, securitization volumes, credit supply figures, and profitability metrics, with panel regression analysis employed to determine patterns and their impacts on each other.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The results of this study could propose:

- **Insights for Policymakers:** Although numerous regulatory initiatives have been implemented to foster the healthy evolution of securitization markets, there remains a potential need for additional scholarly investigation. The findings in this study may offer insights for policymakers regarding the regulatory framework governing banks' securitization practices and capital requirements.
- **Strategic Value for intermediaries:** By understanding the effects of securitization on capital structure and profitability, banking institutions can better strategize their operations, remuneration, and risk management approaches.
- **Academic Contribution:** This research aims to contribute to academic literature by providing empirical evidence on the impacts of securitization within the banking industry, potentially filling gaps identified in previous studies.

1.8 Structure of the study

This research was divided into five chapters. The first chapter is the introduction, followed by theoretical framework and literature review. In the third chapter, we have presented our methodologies. In the fourth chapter, we have presented the results. Lastly, in the fifth chapter, we have summarized the results and included concluding remarks.

2. Theoretical Framework Literature Review

Many of the academic interest in securitization intensified post 2008 global financial crisis, with a strong emphasis on its implications for aggregate liquidity, capitalization, and systemic risk. Building on this foundation, the present study shifts focus to the effects of securitization at the bank level, specifically examining how it influences loans, equity, and profitability on bank balance sheets.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This study capitalizes on the theories highlighted below and based on our objectives to examine the link between securitization and three other variables, credit supply, capital constraints, and profitability.

- **Financial Intermediation Theory:** Discussing how banks serve as intermediaries between savers and borrowers and the role of securitization in this process.
- **Risk-Return Trade-Off Theory:** Stating the tendency for banks to balance the return on assets with the risk associated with their asset portfolio, including loans.
- **Gorton-Pennacchi Model:** Explaining the markets with limited availability of information and uncertain returns effect on private investors.
- **Akerlof Market for Lemons Theory:** Rationalizing the adverse selection problem and its relevance to securitization in the banking industry.

2.2 Literature Review

In our literature review, we focus on our three main variables relating to securitization. We analyzed academic studies that focused on the relationship between securitization and bank lending, capital constraints, and bank profits.

2.2.1 Securitization and credit supply

Since the 1970s, securitization has played a central role in shifting banks from a traditional originate-to-hold model to an originate-to-distribute approach. This shift has the potential to expand lending capacity and improve operational efficiency. In this study, we explore the relationship between securitization activity and actual loan volumes.

Loutskina, E. (2011)⁽³⁾ proved that the higher ability of banks to securitize loans has led to a decrease in their holding of liquid assets on balance sheets, therefore an increase in their lending capacity which is both statistically and economically significant. This might not be the case after Basel III regulatory framework which made securitization more costly for banks. The academic study went short of describing the increase or decrease in credit supply and categorizing the loans by products, however, it focused more on liquidity and funding in a holistic way. Our eighteen years data covers before and after Basel III, and our study does not cover the capacity but covers the actual loan supply volume.

Critically, Loutskina, E., and Strahan, P. E. (2009)⁽⁴⁾ argued that the credit supply became less dependent of the bank's financial health, meaning that banks reduced dependency of credit supply on a bank's financial condition due to the liquidity provided by the securitization market. Banks used liquid deposits to originate illiquid loans and transfer them into liquid assets through securitization. We are consistent with the study in focusing on the credit supply even though the data conducted was only up to 2004.

Considering the evolving nature of financial markets pre and post both the financial crisis and the Basel III regulations, further research was necessary to understand the current implications of these findings at the end of these two eras.

We examined whether securitization increased or decreased credit supply and raised intuitive arguments of the reasons for our results.

2.2.2 Securitization and bank capital constraints

Capital constraints, primarily in the form of regulatory capital requirements, are a fundamental aspect of banking regulation. These constraints, which have become particularly stringent post-2008 financial crisis, are designed to ensure that banks maintain a healthy level of capital reserves relative to their risk-weighted assets. Basel III imposed risk-weighted capital adequacy ratios, whereby the to-be-held capital by the banks would be in proportion to the riskiness of its assets. Securitization enhances the bank's ability for capital relief because this option allows the selling of loans so that there will be more money available for other purposes. That is, by selling off riskier loans, banks are thereby able to lower their regulatory capital requirements and hence release capital for further lending. This theoretical benefit underpins the claim that securitization enhances bank ability for capital relief and examines the relationship between securitization and capital constraints in banks.

The essence of this relationship between securitization and capital constraints has been brought out by Acharya, et. (2013)⁽⁵⁾ who raised critical opinion based on which the dynamics become apparent between securitization practices and regulatory capital requirements. The paper highlights that banks were motivated by regulatory arbitrage - structuring guarantees to reduce regulatory capital requirements while providing recourse to bank balance sheets for outside investors. This tactic was more dominant among banks with less capital.

This paper seeks to build on their findings, exploring the manner that securitization was initially meant as a risk distribution mechanism and has since evolved within the confines of capital regulation. We shall look at the implications of this evolution on capital and securitization in our study.

2.2.3 Securitization and profits

One can argue that the most factor influencing a bank's management is profitability. We thought that it would be helpful to examine the effect of securitization on profitability as well as credit supply and capital constraints. This will help us in studying the motivation behind why banks securitize. Banks, by moving assets off their balance sheets, reduce the capital reserve requirements, increase liquidity, and even maybe increase profitability.

Efing's study (2016)⁽⁶⁾ sheds light on how banks can arbitrage regulatory frameworks, like the Basel Accords, through securitization. While his analysis is centered on German banks and Asset-Backed Securities (ABS), similar dynamics can be observed in the U.S. For instance, American banks have been known to securitize assets to reduce the risk-weighted assets on their balance sheets, thereby

lowering their capital requirements under Basel III regulations. This strategic maneuvering not only helps in meeting regulatory standards but also enhances profitability. The study shows that constrained banks, those with capital adequacy ratios close to the regulatory minimum, were found to engage more aggressively in risk weight arbitrage. This behavior allowed these banks to significantly increase their return on equity, reflecting a potential increase in bank risk. Meaning, bigger banks with more capital constraints opted to increase their profits.

Banks which are heavily involved in securitization can create profits through an outright sale of the assets with a premium over the book value, or it can be through a fee-based revenue from the underwriting of the transaction.

Even with regulation around remunerations, the main goal for a banks' management is not only to maximize a shareholder's wealth through EPS and ROE growth, but also not to lose market share. Banks can always react to the regulation. In this case, the banks can game the system. Meaning, management in banks can resort to decisions to maintain income at target levels.

3. Methodology

This study examines US banks engaged in securitization between 2000 and 2017 based on panel regression analysis. We used a linear panel regression to examine the link between different variables and to observe the behavior changes over the years.

Considering the above, we gathered data of securitization of CLO/CDO deals in the US banks through the source of Asset-Backed Alert ⁽⁷⁾. We focused only on banks and excluded other financial institutions like insurance and asset management companies to have a unified regulation and capitalization consideration. We used S&P Capital research portal ⁽⁸⁾ to extract the financial statements of the US banks used in this study. The banks were grouped into two main groups:

Group (A) Banks which securitized between the years 2000 to 2017.

Group (B) Banks which did not securitize between the years 2000 to 2017.

Group A banks includes US and non-US banks operating in the US markets. For group A banks we used all consolidated financials. We converted all consolidated financials in different currencies to US dollar value. We found a big gap between group A and group B banks in terms of balance sheet size

and profitability values shown in Figure 3.1. The gap between group A and B could be evidence that securitization is an innovative and complex way of banking, done by big players who have the know-how and the resources required for securitization. We noticed that group A banks did not securitize their assets on a yearly basis as there were some gaps in the years observed.

Figure 3.1

Source: Author's own calculation

Despite the big difference in size between the two groups, and the fact that group A has more resources in doing business, group B has on average a higher loan to assets ratio and equity to assets ratio. Meaning even though group B is much smaller in size and capabilities, group B banks had a higher credit supply and capitalization ratios on average as shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2

Source: Author's own calculation

We used loans to assets ratio to measure credit supply, equity to assets ratio to measure capital constraints, and finally net profit to measure profitability.

3.1 Securitization and credit supply

To classify the banks into different groups, a dummy variable is generated that takes one if the bank has ever securitized between 2000-2017 and zero otherwise. We want to distinguish between the nature of assets of being liquid or illiquid assets on the banks' balance sheets and the amount of credit supply in dollars terms. We used net loans to assets ratio as a measure for credit supply. We used year as FE to capture the time-invariant characteristics of the bank such as the overall riskiness and business model. The year as control variable account for other factors that might influence the credit supply, such as economic conditions, Monetary cycle, bank size, capitalization, and risk profile.

Variables:

1. Securitization Dummy (non-time variant), group (A)=1, group (B)= 0. - dependent variable
2. Loans to Assets Ratio: A percentage of loans to total assets- independent variable
3. Total Assets: Logarithm of total assets- independent variable
4. Cash: Logarithm of cash- independent variable

The dependent variable is the Securitization dummy. The independent variables are loans to assets ratio, total assets, and cash. We added assets and cash variables to study the effect of the dependent variable on a multi-level that will help us with the results. The standard error is adjusted to clustering the banks.

Data STATA input: *reg securitizerdummy Loansassetsratio Logassets Logcash i.Year, vce (cluster , Bank)*

No. of Obs.	R square	Root MSE	F (20,32)
305	0.8221	0.215	13.6

		Coefficient (β)	SE	t	p-Value
Dependent variable	Securitization dummy				
Independent variable	Loans assets ratio	-0.3656798	0.337375	-1.1	0.287
Independent variable	Logassets	0.1275438	0.041312	3.09	0.004
Independent variable	Logcash	0.0141413	0.033416	0.42	0.675
Years	2001	-0.048879	0.039466	-1.2	0.225
	2002	-0.0477723	0.041597	-1.2	0.259
	2003	-0.1321786	0.05782	-2.3	0.029
	2004	-0.0619442	0.034154	-1.8	0.079
	2005	-0.0464723	0.042062	-1.1	0.277
	2006	-0.0453083	0.046787	-1	0.34
	2007	-0.0845156	0.045861	-1.8	0.075
	2008	-0.1383421	0.050452	-2.7	0.01
	2009	-0.1749611	0.046271	-3.8	0.001
	2010	-0.1792154	0.048491	-3.7	0.001
	2011	-0.1648642	0.047003	-3.5	0.001
	2012	-0.140727	0.053482	-2.6	0.013
	2013	-0.1626639	0.051889	-3.1	0.004
	2014	-0.1834345	0.066235	-2.8	0.009
	2015	-0.174356	0.07718	-2.3	0.031
	2016	-0.1564686	0.076871	-2	0.05
	2017	-0.1625756	0.068062	-2.4	0.023
	_cons	-1.754623	0.632895	-2.8	0.009

Figure 3.3

Source: Author's own calculation

Number of observations (obs): The regression was run on 305 observations.

F-statistic and Prob > F: The F-statistic is 13.60 with a corresponding p-value (Prob > F) practically 0. This suggests that the overall regression is statistically significant, and that the independent variables, collectively, have a strong predictive influence on the dependent variable.

R-squared: The R-squared value is 0.8221, indicating that approximately 82.21% of the variability in the dependent variable securitizer dummy can be explained by the model.

Root MSE: The root mean square error is 0.215, which indicates the standard deviation of the regression residuals.

Std. err.: The standard error of the coefficient estimate, which measures the average amount that the coefficient estimate varies across different samples.

The regression output also includes coefficients for various independent variables:

Loansassetsratio: This coefficient is not statistically significant ($p > |t| = 0.287$), indicating that it is not a significant predictor of the dependent variable in this model.

Logassets: The coefficient is 0.1275 and is statistically significant ($p > |t| = 0.004$), with also high confidence level, implying that for each unit increase in the logarithm of assets, the dependent variable, or group (A), increases by approximately 0.1275 units, holding all other variables constant.

Logcash: This has a non-significant coefficient ($p > |t| = 0.675$).

Year fixed effects: The regression includes fixed effects. The coefficients for the years 2008, and 2010 to 2014 are negative and statistically significant, suggesting that these years have a negative effect on the dependent variable compared to the base year (which is not shown, but is likely one of the years before 2001).

Constant (_cons): The constant or intercept is -1.7546, with a p-value of 0.009, indicating that when all other variables are held at zero, the expected value of the dependent variable, group (A), is -1.7546, and this effect is statistically significant.

3.2 Securitization and capital constraints

To analyze the link between securitization & capital constraints. João Santos and Andrew Winton (2019)⁽⁹⁾ defined capital as the ratio of equity to assets. We followed the same concept in this study for consistency and completeness across the data.

We used year as Fixed Effects to capture the time-invariant characteristics of the bank such as the overall riskiness and business model. The year as control variable account for other factors that might influence the credit supply, such as economic conditions, Monetary cycle, bank size, capitalization, and risk profile.

Variables:

1. Securitization Dummy, group (A)=1, group (B)= 0. - dependent variable
2. Equity to Assets Ratio. - independent variable.

To study the effect of capital constraints on securitization, we used equity to assets ratio to measure capital and to examine the link between securitization capital constraints. The fixed effect is given to the years to control the time effect. The standard error is adjusted by banks.

Data STATA input: *reg securitizerdummy EquityAssetsratio i.Year, vce (cluster Bank)*

No. of Obs.	R square	Root MSE	F (18,32)
305	0.3344	0.41435	9.59

		Coefficient (β)	SE	t	p-Value
Dependent variable	Securitization dummy				
Independent variable	Equity Assets ratio	-5.142033	2.012285	-2.6	0.016
Years	2001	-0.0181812	0.051788	-0.4	0.728
	2002	0.0225552	0.084228	0.27	0.791
	2003	-0.0550146	0.083237	-0.7	0.513
	2004	0.0388755	0.051888	0.75	0.459
	2005	0.1316518	0.068038	1.93	0.062
	2006	0.1674564	0.081596	2.05	0.048
	2007	0.0977052	0.075495	1.29	0.205
	2008	0.0396474	0.082518	0.48	0.634
	2009	-0.0722448	0.096949	-0.8	0.462
	2010	-0.0716738	0.107813	-0.7	0.511
	2011	-0.0631676	0.114203	-0.6	0.584
	2012	-0.0298488	0.120283	-0.3	0.806
	2013	0.0223584	0.117107	0.19	0.85
	2014	-0.0311588	0.133325	-0.2	0.817
	2015	-0.0929289	0.153269	-0.6	0.549
	2016	-0.0195573	0.15296	-0.1	0.899
	2017	0.0620158	0.140544	0.44	0.662
	_cons	0.8644135	0.182669	4.73	0

Figure 3.4

Source: Author's own calculation

Number of observations (obs): The regression was run on 305 observations.

Model Significance: The model is statistically significant as indicated by the F-statistic ($F(18, 32) = 9.59$, $\text{Prob} > F = 0.0000$), meaning the explanatory variables as a whole are likely to be related to the dependent variable.

R-squared: The R-squared value is 0.3344, which means that about 33.44% of the variability in the dependent variable is accounted for by the model. This suggests a moderate explanatory power of the model.

Root MSE: The Root Mean Square Error is 0.41435, which provides an estimate of the standard deviation of the residuals. This number indicates the typical distance between the observed values and the values predicted by the model.

Std. err.: The standard error of the coefficient estimate, which measures the average amount that the coefficient estimate varies across different samples.

Coefficients:

EquityAssetsratio: This variable has a significant negative effect on the dependent variable, with a coefficient of -5.142033 ($p = 0.016$). This implies that as the EquityAssetsratio increases by one unit,

the dependent variable decreases by approximately 5.142033 units, holding other variables constant.

Year fixed effects: Most years do not show a statistically significant effect on the dependent variable, as their p-values are above the conventional threshold of 0.05.

However, the year 2006 shows a positive and significant coefficient (1.674564, $p = 0.048$), suggesting that something in 2006 had a positive effect on the dependent variable compared to the omitted base year.

Constant: The constant term is highly significant ($p = 0.000$), with a coefficient of 0.8644135. This indicates that when all other variables are held at zero, the expected value of the dependent variable is 0.8644135.

3.3 Securitization and profits

We study the link between securitization and profits. To measure profitability, we used net income vs. securitization.

We used year as Fixed Effects to capture the time-invariant characteristics of the bank such as the overall riskiness and business model. The year as control variable accounts for other factors that might influence the credit supply, such as economic conditions, monetary cycle, bank size, capitalization, and risk profile.

Variables:

1. Log Net Income (logarithmic net income) - dependent variable
2. Securitization Dummy - independent variable

To study the effect of securitization activity on profitability, we used logarithmic net income to measure profitability. The fixed effect is given to the years to control the time effect. The standard error is adjusted by banks.

Data STATA input: reg Lognetincome securitizerdummy i.Year , vce (cluster Bank)

No. of Obs.	R square	Root MSE	F (18,32)
288	0.732	1.257	22.1

		Coefficient (β)	SE	t	p-Value
Dependent variable	Log net income				
Independent variable	Securitization dummy	4.028721	0.460169	8.75	0
Year	2001	-0.1464977	0.170568	-0.9	0.397
	2002	-0.3861719	0.314774	-1.2	0.229
	2003	0.0690004	0.285583	0.24	0.811
	2004	0.2968952	0.211609	1.4	0.17
	2005	0.5397828	0.186287	2.9	0.007
	2006	0.6754023	0.191327	3.53	0.001
	2007	0.4599843	0.269658	1.71	0.098
	2008	0.2820861	0.251029	1.12	0.269
	2009	0.2696746	0.40157	0.67	0.507
	2010	0.5168605	0.2967	1.74	0.091
	2011	0.3998297	0.280132	1.43	0.163
	2012	0.3005107	0.332033	0.91	0.372
	2013	0.6806008	0.254742	2.67	0.012
	2014	0.8834439	0.249051	3.55	0.001
	2015	0.5791147	0.287376	2.02	0.052
	2016	0.9345149	0.247728	3.77	0.001
	2017	0.9040879	0.246131	3.67	0.001
	_cons	10.81171	0.43884	24.6	0

Figure 3.5

Source: Author's own calculation

Securitization and profits data analysis:

Number of observations (Number of obs): There are 288 observations used in the regression.

Degrees of Freedom F (18, 32): The model has 18 explanatory variables (including the year dummies) and 32 degrees of freedom left for the error term.

F-statistic (22.10) and Prob > F (0.0000): The F-statistic is quite high, and the associated probability is very low, indicating the model has significant predictive power.

R-squared (0.7322): The model explains 73.22% of the variability of the dependent variable, which is a good level of explanatory power.

Root MSE (1.2576): The root mean square error is relatively low, suggesting that the predicted values are, on average, close to the observed values.

Coefficients:

Securitization dummy (4.028721): The securitization dummy variable has a large and statistically significant coefficient (p-value < 0.05), suggesting that being a securitizer, or group A, is associated with an increase in the dependent variable, net income in a logarithmic format.

Year Fixed Effects:

The year variables capture annual effects that are not otherwise accounted for by the model.

Significant coefficients for certain years (e.g., 2006, 2010, 2013, 2015, 2016, 2017) indicate that there are differences in those years compared to the year 2000.

Constant (Intercept) (10.81171):

The constant term is highly significant, which suggests that when all other variables are 0, the dependent variable, or the log net income, is expected to be approximately 10.81171 on the log scale.

4. Empirical Results

4.1 Securitization and bank lending

Our panel regression reveals that no significant relationship exists between credit supply and being a regular securitizer, represented group (A) in the methodology. To put it another way, banks involved in securitization did not generally increase their overall loans. However, we observed a positive correlation between securitization and higher total asset size. Meaning, banks securitized to increase overall assets but not loans in specific. This suggests that large banks securitizing assets might be driven by motives other than increasing credit supply. Loutskina, E., and Strahan, P. E. (2009) ⁽¹⁰⁾ mentioned that banks securitize for liquidity reasons. The driver for securitization might be to generate liquidity, not to increase credit supply. Therefore, we reject the hypothesis that securitization increases credit supply.

To illustrate the result in Figure 4.1, we ran a scatter plot to show the relationship between the logarithmic amount securitized on the x-axis and the loans to assets ratio on the y-axis. The trend is negative sloping which indicates a negative relationship between the amount securitized and credit supply. The non-security group B are shown as outliers in the graph near the y-axis.

Figure 4.1

Source: Author's own calculation

4.2 Securitization and capital constraints

In the previous methodology, we rejected the hypothesis that securitization increased credit supply, Now, we will test the other hypothesis if securitization relaxes capital constraints or not.

The regression model indicates that the Equity assets ratio has a statistically significant negative impact on the dependent variable. The year 2006 is the only year with a significant positive impact compared to the base year (likely before 2001, which is not included in the model). The constant term is significant, and the model explains a moderate proportion of the variance in the dependent variable. The model's predictive power is moderate as indicated by the R-squared value.

The negative sign of the coefficient suggests that banks involved in securitization activities tend to have a lower equity-to-assets ratio compared to banks that do not securitize assets. In practical terms, this implies that for each bank engaged in securitization, the equity-to-assets ratio is lower by approximately 6.6 percentage points on average, holding all else constant. The 95% confidence interval for this estimate ranges from -0.0840939 to -0.0290876, reinforcing the precision of our estimate and indicating that the effect is not limited. Therefore, we confirm the validity of the proposed hypothesis based on empirical evidence.

The graph below, Figure 4.2, shows the relationship between the logarithmic amount securitized +1 on the x-axis and the equity to assets ratio on the y-axis. The trend is negative slopping which indicates a negative relationship between the amount securitized and capital. The non-security group B are shown as outliers in the graph near the y-axis.

Figure 4.2

Source: Author's own calculation

4.3 Securitization and bank profits

The model indicates a significant relationship between the net income and securitization, meaning that Securitization is a strong predictor of Banks' income. Either revenue is the driver for securitization, or is it the other way around, banks who securitize tend to have higher revenues.

The banks engaged in securitization group (A) significantly increased their net income. This might be due to pressure from shareholders. The increase in the coefficient post 2013 means that the rate of increase in net income has risen post 2013. Basel III implemented tougher regulations in 2013, related to the higher capital requirements, the liquidity ratios, and the leverage ratio. Banks might have focused more on underwriting, generating income through securitization, while complying with Basel requirements. Thus, the data supports the hypothesis.

Figure 4.3 illustrates the relationship between the logarithmic amount securitized +1 on the x-axis and the logarithmic net income +1 on the y-axis. The trend is positively sloping which indicates a positive relationship between the amount securitized and profitability. The non-security group B are shown as outliers in the graph near the y-axis.

Figure 4.3

Source: Author's own calculation

5. Conclusion

This research challenges the commonly held view that securitization directly boosts credit supply. Our findings suggest that banks may instead use securitization to manage liquidity or replace existing assets, rather than expand lending. We observed a negative correlation between securitization and capital adequacy, indicating that lower-capitalized banks are more likely to securitize as a strategy to meet regulatory requirements. In contrast, securitization showed a positive association with profitability, reflecting shareholder pressure to enhance returns.

Overall, this analysis provides a nuanced understanding of securitization's role in U.S. banking. While it serves as an effective tool for capital management, there is little evidence to support its use as a catalyst for increased lending. Its positive impact on profits underscores the influence of shareholder expectations and the strategic balance of risk and reward.

These findings highlight the importance of maintaining regulatory equilibrium, ensuring responsible bank management, and promoting informed investor participation. Together, these elements are essential to support financial system stability and sustainable growth in an increasingly complex banking environment.

5.1 Summary of findings

In conclusion, our empirical findings suggest a significant and negative association between a bank's securitization activities and its equity-to-assets ratio. This result could be indicative of a variety of economic behaviors or regulatory environments that lead securitizing banks to maintain different capital structures than their non-securitizing counterparts. For instance, securitizing banks might have lower equity-to-assets ratios due to the off-balance-sheet treatment of securitized assets, which may reduce the apparent riskiness and capital requirements of these banks.

Alternatively, these banks may be engaging in securitization precisely because they have less capital and are thus looking to manage their risk and capital ratios more aggressively. Further research, perhaps using more granular data or different methodological approaches, could help disentangle these and other potential explanations for our findings.

5.2 Limitation of the Study

Our main concern of securitization remains operations taking place within the parameters of the shadow banking system. Positioning itself within such a bank presents a substantial issue in rightly reporting data attributed to such innovative financial tools. Such considerations prompt valid questions: Were financial institutions engaging primarily in securitization as a strategy with good intention to counterbalance against the bad effects of adverse selection? Was it instead the motive of securitizing to increase the credit supply, to assist in regulations concerned with limitation of capital, or maybe to diversify and increase their capability to generate revenues?

It is important to note that the model used in the study could suffer from omitted variable bias if there are other key variables that are not included in the model that can influence the results like risk appetite, regulations, or market conditions.

Using net loans to assets ratio as a measure for credit supply had a downside effect since the loans used were on consolidated basis and without distinguishing between the types of loans. Although securitization involves the pooling of various types of assets (like mortgages, credit card debts, or loans), we took net loans (gross loans minus loans loss reserve) and compared it to total assets as a percentage ratio. The study discounted the various types of assets, and we took the net loans as an aggregate figure.

5.3 Suggestion for future research

It would be helpful to capture the control variables like debt to asset ratio for example to account for the time-varying riskiness of the bank. It would also be useful to examine macroeconomic controls such as GDP growth and inflation.

Using capital-to-risk weighted assets ratio (CRAR) could enhance the study more instead of using equity to assets ratio.

Reference list

1. John Kerschner, Busting the bias against US securitized, Janus Henderson [online] Available from <https://www.janushenderson.com/en-us/advisor/article/busting-the-bias-against-us-securitized/> (Accessed 14 January 2024)
2. Gary Gorton, George Pennacchi (1990) Financial Intermediaries and Liquidity Creation, *The Journal of Finance*, 45: 49-71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1990.tb05080.x>
3. Elena Loutskina (2011), The role of securitization in bank liquidity and funding management, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 100(3), 663-684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2011.02.005>
4. LOUTSKINA, E. and STRAHAN, P.E. (2009), Securitization and the Declining Impact of Bank Finance on Loan Supply: Evidence from Mortgage Originations. *The Journal of Finance*, 64: 861-889. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.2009.01451.x>
5. Acharya, V. V., Schnabl, P., and Suarez, G. (2013) "Securitization without risk transfer" published in *Journal of Financial Economics*, 107 (3), 515-536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2012.09.004>.
6. Efung, Matthias (2016), Arbitraging the Basel Securitization Framework: Evidence from German ABS Investment (September 1, 2016). ESRB: Working Paper Series No. 2016/22. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3723367>
7. Assets alert. [online] Available from <https://greenstreet.com/news/asset-backed-alert?breakdownId=76> (Accessed 15 October 2023)
8. S&P capital IQ. [online] Available from www.capitaliq.spglobal.com (Accessed 15 November 2023)
9. João A C Santos and Andrew (2019), Bank Capital, Borrower Power, and Loan Rates, *The Review of Financial Studies*, Volume 32, Issue 11, November 2019, Pages 4501–4541, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhz001>
10. Elena Loutskina and Philip E. Strahan, (2009), Securitization and the Declining Impact of Bank Finance on Loan Supply: Evidence from Mortgage Originations, *Journal of Finance*, 64, (2), 861-889. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1080-8620.2004.00102.x>